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Greening the Belt and Road Initiative and the 2030 Agenda: China's Environmental Diplomacy Discourse in Focus¹

Abstract

To address concerns about the Belt and Road Initiative's (BRI's) negative environmental impact, China created an environmental governance architecture to transform it into a climate-neutral and nature-positive "Green BRI". Through this architecture and also bilateral engagements with BRI states, Beijing produced a distinct environmental diplomacy discourse. This discourse revolves around the synergies between the BRI and the United Nations 2030 Agenda and Sustainable Development Goals (2030 Agenda; SDGs), including environmental goals 7 (affordable and clean energy) and 13 (climate action). Despite Beijing's discursive commitment to the 2030 Agenda, significant barriers hinder the BRI's accomplishments towards these SDGs.

Keywords: 2030 Agenda; Belt and Road Initiative; China; environmental diplomacy; foreign policy; Global South.

Introduction

To address concerns about the Belt and Road Initiative's (BRI's) environmental impact, China constructed an environmental governance architecture to create a climate-neutral and nature-positive

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“Green BRI”. Using this and its bilateral engagement with BRI states, Beijing also generated an environmental diplomacy discourse. This paper gives an assessment of China’s discourse in practice, by focusing on synergies between the BRI and the United Nations 2030 Agenda and Sustainable Development Goals (2030 Agenda; SDGs). China’s environmental diplomacy discourse views the BRI as a means to foster SDG implementation in participating states. This is important, as over half of the 140 BRI states are found in the Global South, are typically mid- to low-income countries with rather poor environmental profiles and are weakly integrated into international organisations.

While there is evidence of a commitment to the 2030 Agenda in Beijing’s BRI-related multilateral and bilateral environmental diplomacy discourse, this paper questions the existence in practice of a 2030 Agenda-BRI connection. To highlight both evidence and barriers, this paper uses an array of BRI-related primary sources to look at two environmental SDGs – goals 7 (affordable and clean energy) and 13 (climate action) – both of which resonate with key environmental challenges in the roadmap to the Green BRI and the main themes in China's environmental diplomacy discourse.

Since the launch of the BRI in 2013, commentary on if and how it aligns with the SDGs has proliferated. Some authors look at the “systemic” nature of BRI – policy coordination, connectivity, unimpeded trade, financial integration, and people-to-people bonds (Hong 2017; United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs [UN DESA] 2019; Lewis *et al.* 2021, 58-79). Other literature identifies BRI’s impact on particular SDGs, however SDGs 7 and 13 are a marginal part of such mapping exercises (Gu *et al.* 2019). Pingfan Hong (2017) links facilities connectivity that, among others, is about “promoting green and low carbon infrastructure construction by taking into full account the impact of climate change” with SDG 7 and 13 (6). Additionally, *Progress Report on the Belt and Road Initiative in Support of the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* (UN DESA 2019) distinguishes achievements in SDG 13 as aligning with people-to-people bonds potentially strengthened under the BRI.

Literature that discusses the BRI and environmental aspects of sustainability often focuses on “green finance” (Cheung and Hong 2020; Tu *et al.* 2021) and/or “green investment” (Cheng 2023) as key instruments to achieve the green BRI and related SDGs; or provides regional case studies mainly from Global South, with little reference to the BRI's environmental governance architecture and related diplomacy discourse.

While the gap in the literature on BRI-SDG is thin, our paper still aims to try to fill it. We fully acknowledge that Beijing's narrative as a reliable source is questionable, but nevertheless we highlight the need to study what and how China speaks about the environmental impacts of the BRI. This is especially the case in the Global South, in low and middle-income fragile states with poor ecological records that tend to be vulnerable to foreign powers’ influences.

This paper assesses China's discourse in practice, by analysing the synergies between the BRI and the 2030 Agenda. The paper is organised as follows. First, terminology and highlights of the implications of the BRI for the natural environment are identified in the literature. Second, China's multilateral environmental diplomacy, since 2017 (when the Green BRI was announced) is analysed, to demonstrate how Beijing sees the synergy between BRI and the 2030 Agenda – in other words, how it wants this synergy to work with the emphasis being placed on SDGs 7 and 13. Third, it identifies such synergy in China's bilateral environmental discourse. Finally, to emphasise the project's practical barriers, we refer to achievements in SDGs 7 and 13 in the 10 largest receivers of the BRI energy infrastructure.

China's environmental diplomacy discourse shadowing the BRI's environmental impact

The BRI is China's foreign-policy umbrella and a massive connectivity project engaging approximately 140 states. Energy constitutes the key aspect of China's engagements, accounting for 51% and 36% of all of its engagements under the BRI in 2013 and 2023, respectively. Other important sectors include transport (18-27% of all engagements between 2013-2023) and metals and mining (6-9% of all engagements between 2013-2023; Nedopil 2023). The literature emphasizes numerous implications of such infrastructure development for the natural environment:

- Reduced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions due to the use of new clean technologies, resulting from the BRI's implementation (Coenen *et al.* 2020, 3-17; Wu *et al.* 2021) – e.g., solar energy systems (Eyler 2019).
- An increase in GHG emissions caused by the BRI's transport activities (such as transportation of goods on roads and railways) and energy infrastructure (Coenen *et al.* 2020, 3-17; Hughes 2019, 883-894; Zhai 2021; Zhang *et al.* 2017, 1107; Zhou *et al.* 2018), especially coal-based facilities (Ali *et al.* 2022; Rauf *et al.* 2020; Kalantzakos *et al.* 2023, 3-22)
- Air and water pollution resulting from the use of chemicals for infrastructure construction (Ali *et al.* 2022; Lechner *et al.* 2019).
- Deforestation due to the construction of roads, rail lines, etc. (Ali *et al.* 2022; Hughes 2019, 883-894).
- The effects on wildlife and habitats caused by poorly planned infrastructure of both land and marine routes (Coenen *et al.* 2020, 3-17; Hughes 2019, 883-894; Lechner *et al.* 2019; Zhai 2021).
- Flooding, soil erosion and landslides caused by the construction of roads, highways and railway bridges (Zhai 2021).

- Negative spillover into fishing, farming and agriculture caused by infrastructure construction – e.g., new dams (Zhai 2021).
- Water shortages due to the construction and use of raw materials (Ali *et al.* 2022; Coenen *et al.*, 2020, 3-17; Howard and Howard 2016, 1-12; Hughes 2019), coal-fired power plants (Alkon *et al.* 2019, 1101-1109) and mining activities (Pike 2017).
- Illegal wildlife trade resulting indirectly from the construction of new roads (new supply corridors) and the destruction of natural habitats (Farhadinia *et al.* 2019, 1267-1268).

Beijing has produced an environmental diplomacy discourse via the BRI's environmental governance architecture, which has significantly expanded since the announcement of *The Guidance on Promoting Green Belt and Road* in 2017. This infrastructure encompasses the following elements (i) Chinese domestic governance entities, including ministries, agencies and banking institutions under the State Council; (ii) international governance structures, including new and existing cooperation networks, platforms and mechanisms; and (iii) soft laws – e.g., policies and guidelines (Coenen *et al.* 2020, 3-17). This framework aims to establish a Green BRI, which is intended to be climate-neutral, produce zero GHG emissions, be nature-positive and protective of biodiversity, and improve people's livelihoods (Green Finance & Development Centre 2024a).

Environmental diplomacy discourse, spread via the abovementioned architecture, distinguishes various policy concepts with emphasis given to “ecological civilisation” (Weatherley and Bauer 2021, 2115-2132) and the 2030 Agenda. The first serves as a compass for China's green trajectory at home and abroad and is recognised as an attempt to “Sinicise” environmentalism and influence global discourse. The term “‘ecological civilisation’ wiggled its way into the lexicon of the international community at the United Nations Environment Programme Governing Council meeting in 2013 in Nairobi... Although delegates were confused—and some shocked—to hear this term, the Chinese delegation reassured their counterparts that ecological civilisation is a more comprehensive expression of sustainable development” (Wang-Kaeding 2018, 24). However, in BRI-related environmental diplomacy discourse, the notion of ecological civilisation is presented as a concept aligned with the 2030 Agenda. While such discourse may help Beijing popularise its own ecological ideas, the 2030 Agenda, with its 17 SDGs, is known to a broader international audience and can facilitate a bridge between the BRI and international environmental governance. Therefore, by coupling the 2030 Agenda with the BRI, Beijing makes its discourse more efficient in convincing foreign actors to hold pro-environmental intentions aligned with the BRI.

In the context of the BRI-2030 Agenda alignment, SDGs 7 and 13 resonate with main themes in China's environmental diplomacy discourse, namely, clean renewable energy and climate change. Interestingly, China's BRI energy engagement has changed significantly since 2013. China's BRI-related investment in coal energy decreased from 45% in 2015 to 0% in early 2023. Conversely, solar,

wind and hydropower energy investments have increased from 33% in 2018 to 77% in 2022 (Nedopil 2023). This shift, if it becomes a trend, will both enhance the BRI's potential to contribute to SDGs 7 and 13, and resonate with Beijing's environmental diplomacy discourse. Furthermore, the aforementioned SDGs are interlinked in the BRI context and beyond. Deploying renewable and clean energy aligns with SDG 7 targets and simultaneously contributes to the reduction of GHG emissions, which is one of the SDG 13 indicators. These SDG 7 targets include:

- 7.1. Ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services.
- 7.2. Increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix.
- 7. a. Enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, advanced and cleaner fossil fuel technology and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology.
- 7. b. Expand infrastructure and upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services to all developing countries, particularly the least developed countries, small island developing states and land-locked developing countries, in accordance with their respective programs of support (UN SDGs n.d.).

While the BRI-2030 Agenda coupling works in the environmental diplomacy discourse, it is primarily each nation's responsibility to implement the SDGs (Schaller, 2019); thus, the expectation that countries (e.g., China) will help their peers achieve their goals may be unrealistic. Nevertheless, “foreign policy—especially vis-à-vis low-income, fragile countries, which suffer from both powerlessness in addressing the SDGs and high sensitivity to external actors' behaviour – can significantly affect countries' capabilities in achieving the SDGs, in both positive and negative ways” (Nitza-Makowska 2020, 377-382). This argument is especially poignant in the BRI context because such criteria apply to most of the BRI-participating countries from the Global South. Further, all environmental SDGs, including goals 7 (affordable and clean energy), 12 (responsible consumption and production), 13 (climate action) and 15 (life on land) have been recognised as those that “are expected to be more strongly linked to connectivity and global challenges” (Becker *et al.* 2021), which means that their implementation is prone to be affected by external factors. Despite the apparent interdependence between foreign policy and SDG implementation, “the foreign policy dimensions of the 2030 Agenda have not been sufficiently broached by foreign ministries to date” (Carius *et al.* 2018, 1). This leads to the question of whether the BRI is an example of how a foreign policy strategy can influence SDG implementation. To what extent does this synergy apply to the environmental SDGs, especially goals 7 and 13? Does this synergy have a positive or negative impact on the implementation of the 2030 Agenda – specifically these SDGs – given the enormous environmental challenges related to the BRI?

Multilateral environmental diplomacy – The SDG-BRI roadmap

The China Council for International Cooperation on Environment and Development (CCICED), a high-level international advisory body working under the Government of China, has laid out a roadmap to achieve synergy between the 2030 Agenda and the BRI. This roadmap includes policy communication, strategic alignments, capacity-building and project management between Beijing and the BRI states (CCICED Secretariat, 2022). These elements are described below to highlight the existence of numerous elements of the BRI's environmental governance architecture that are devoted to achieving the BRI-2030 Agenda alignment.

Policy communication among BRI states requires cooperation platforms such as the BRI International Green Development Coalition (BRIGC) – designed specifically to facilitate the implementation of SDGs in BRI host countries. The BRIGC (2023) operates under the supervision of the Ministry of Ecology and Environment of the People's Republic of China (MEE) and the Ministry of Civil Affairs (MCA). So far, except from Chinese actors, the BRIGC has gathered “over 70 overseas institutions such as government departments of BRI participating countries, international organizations, think tanks and businesses” (CCICED Secretariat 2022). ClientEarth (2022, 6) distinguishes the main achievements of the BRIGC, namely, issuing the *Green Development Guidance for BRI Projects Baseline Study Report (GDG)*, *The Application Guide for Enterprises and Financial Institutions* and the *Guide for Railways and Highways Infrastructure Sectors*. While these and other publications of the BRIGC do not refer directly to the 2030 Agenda, their main themes include low-carbon transition, green energy and climate cooperation under the BRI, which align with SDGs 7 and 13. By strengthening policy communication on these themes, the BRI can influence the implementation of SDG 13.2 target by enhancing cooperation and providing assistance in integrating climate change measures into national policies (UN SDGs n.d.).

Strategic alignment provides mechanisms to link the BRI with the 2030 Agenda, enforce environmental diplomacy and improve information-sharing through, for instance, the BRI Environmental Big Data Platform. While this platform provides information about the BRI states' green policies and behaviours, it fails to provide data on environmental cooperation under the BRI. For instance, the section on laws and policies mostly includes national policies with scarce relevance to the BRI, such as the National Climate Change Policy of Pakistan in 2012, a year before the announcement of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) – a part of the BRI that stretched across Pakistan – or the Environmental Strategy of India, which is not part of the BRI. Insufficient data on the environmental aspects of bilateral cooperation between China and other BRI states results in opacity surrounding this type of engagement, including the project's implications for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda and selected SDGs.

Capacity-building aims to enforce people-to-people connectivity via the Green Silk Road Envoy Program. This training program was designed for environmental policymakers, scholars, as well as management and technical personnel by the MEE two years before the BRI was announced and then became a significant component of its environmental governance architecture. By 2019, this program trained over 1,000 individuals as the BRI's "green ambassadors" (Jiangze 2019). While this training's content is unknown, if related to climate change mitigation, it could contribute to the implementation of the SDG 13.3 target by increasing awareness and human and institutional capacity for climate-change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning (UN SDGs n.d.). Additionally, to strengthen people-to-people connectivity and facilitate SDGs' implementation under the BRI, the Chinese Academy of Sciences, along with 36 other international institutions, launched the Alliance of International Science Organizations (ANSO) in 2018. The ANSO aligns with the 2030 Agenda, aiming "to become an international science organization of global impact in catalyzing and implementing concrete innovative programs, initiatives and actions in Science, Technology, Innovation and Capacity Building (STIC) for the promotion of shared-development and the advancement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals" (ANSO 2024). The ANSO (2022) has 67 member institutions from 48 countries and according to its annual report in 2022 it was involved in over 90 projects and activities worldwide, including 41 collaborative studies, 20 training projects and 33 science-based reports and studies. Most of these projects directly or indirectly refer to SDGs, including goals 7 and 13. For instance, Bassem Al-Maythaly, from the Royal Scientific Society of Jordan, claims that the ANSO Collaborative Research project *A First Step Valorization of Waste Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide via Its Sustainable Capture* "has contributed to SDG 13 by reducing the harmful effects of CO₂ on the environment and to raising the awareness of solutions for tackling climate change" (ANSO 2022, 29).

Project management aims to improve environmental management and diminish risks to local ecosystems where the BRI infrastructure is constructed. For instance, the Green Light System, provided by China's MEE, and the abovementioned Green Silk Road Envoys Program have contributed to these aims. The Green Light System classifies BRI projects into green, yellow and red categories based on their impacts on pollution, climate change and biodiversity (BRIGC 2020, 38-39). For instance, the construction and operation of coal-fired power production, retrofitting of existing coal-fired power plants and the construction and operation of coal mines are labelled in red (BRIGC 2020, 47-54). By providing this type of infrastructure, the BRI can prevent host countries from implementing SDG 7, specifically the targets that refer to an increase in the share of renewable and clean energy (7.1, 7.2, 7.a, 7.b.).

Multilateral environmental diplomacy—BRI policies and guidelines

BRI-specific policy documents and guidelines involve the 2030 Agenda, SDGs 7 and 13 and related themes (Table 1). These documents are analysed in the following order: (i) documents centred specifically on the BRI’s environmental aspects and those that mention the 2030 Agenda; (ii) those with the same focus but without such reference; (iii) non-environmentally oriented documents that mention the 2030 Agenda; and (iv) documents lacking this reference.

Year	Published by	Name	Reference to the 2030 Agenda	SDG 7 and/or 13 relevance
Environmentally focused policy documents and guidelines				
2017	Ministry of Environmental Protection (MEP; currently MEE), Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC), Ministry of Commerce (MOFCOM)	Guidance on Promoting Green Belt and Road	Yes	SDG 7 and 13
2017	MEP (currently MEE)	The Belt and Road Ecological and Environmental Cooperation Plan	Yes	SDG 7 and 13
2018	Green Finance Initiative & Green Finance Committee (GFC)	Green Investment Principles (GIP) for the Belt and Road	Yes	SDG 7 and 13

2022	NDRC	Opinions on promoting the green development of the Belt and Road Initiative	No	SDG 7 and 13
Non-environmentally oriented policy documents and guidelines				
2017	NDRC, MFA, Ministry of Commerce (MOFCOM)	Vision and Actions on Energy Cooperation in Jointly Building Silk Road Economic Belt and 21st-Century Maritime Silk Road	Yes	SDG 7 and 13
2019	Office of the Leading Group for Promoting the Belt and Road Initiative	The Belt and Road Initiative Progress, Contributions and Prospects	Yes	SDG 7 and 13
2019	Belt and Road Forum Advisory Council	Belt and Road Cooperation: For a Better World	Yes	SDG 7 and 13 (mentioned directly)

Table 1. BRI-specific policies and guidelines

Source: Green Finance & Development Centre. 2024b.

The Belt and Road Ecological and Environmental Cooperation Plan (MEP 2017) and the *Guidance on Promoting Green Belt and Road* (MEP et al. 2017) are entirely devoted to the environmental aspects of the BRI. The Plan highlights the following:

- The synergy between the SDGs and the BRI: “The cooperation on eco-environmental protection under the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative will inject an effective impetus to accomplishment of environmental targets in the [2030] Agenda in countries along the routes... A new pattern of higher-level cooperation on eco-environmental protection among diverse stakeholders will be created in the Belt and Road, thus contributing to the realisation of Sustainable Development Goals” (MEP 2017).

- China's efforts to improve the implementation of the SDGs via the BRI: “To 2030, we will promote cooperation on eco-environmental protection with higher standards and at deeper levels to accomplish the Sustainable Development Goals. We will deepen cooperation in key fields such as environmental pollution control, ecological protection, nuclear and radiation safety, and technological innovation in environmental protection” (MEP 2017).

Similarly, the *Guidance on Promoting Green Belt and Road* assumes that “promoting green belts and roads and strengthening eco-environment protection will help... facilitate joint achievement of 2030 sustainable development goals by countries and regions along the route”. Further, it links the main objectives of the BRI with the 2030 Agenda: “We will, according to the overall requirements of the 'Belt and Road' Initiative and by centring around ecological civilisation, sustainable development goals and relevant environmental protection requirements, coordinate existing domestic and international cooperation mechanisms, leverage on the role of eco-environment protection as a window for international cooperation, strengthen integration of eco-environment protection strategies and plans of countries or regions along the route, and build cooperation and exchange systems” (MEP *et al.* 2017).

The abovementioned two policy documents do not mention particular SDGs; however, they highlight the convergence between the BRI and SDGs 7 and 13. First, both emphasise the BRI's aim of encouraging the enterprises involved in the project to prioritise low-carbon, energy-saving and environmentally friendly materials and processes that resonate with the two SDGs. Second, both highlight the BRI's objective of avoiding environmental risks and disasters, especially in areas that are prone to them, which specifically aligns with SDG target 13.1 (Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters; UN SDGs n.d.). Third, both assume that cooperation in mitigating climate change is part of trade and business relationships under the BRI, which aligns with SDG 13. Moreover, the *Guidance on Promoting Green Belt and Road* emphasises Beijing's attachment to the environmental quality of the BRI achieved via popularisation of the “energy conservation and environmental protection standards and practice in such sectors as green transport, green building and clean energy... and improved green and low-carbon construction and operation” (MEP *et al.* 2017). These standards and practices align with SDG 7 implementation.

Similarly to the *Guidelines and the Cooperation Plan, The Green Investment Principles* (GIP) for the BRI, identifies improvements in the 2030 Agenda implementation as its main aim. However, it differentiates from the other two policy documents as it recognises the Global South as its main focus, “Geographical focus of the GIP is countries covered by BRI spanning across Asia, Europe and Africa. Most of the countries are emerging economies who are critical in delivering global climate

change targets and in achieving the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development” (Green Finance Initiative & Green Finance Committee 2018).

Contrary to the abovementioned environmentally oriented policy documents mentioning the 2030 Agenda, the *Opinions on promoting the green development of the Belt and Road Initiative* (NDRC, 2022) mention sustainable development without directly referencing the 2030 Agenda. However, the *Opinions* emphasise the BRI's role in strengthening cooperation to combat climate change and the importance of green energy-saving solutions aligned with SDGs 7 and 13.

Referring exclusively to the BRI's energy infrastructure, *Vision and Actions on Energy Cooperation in Jointly Building Silk Road Economic Belt and 21st-Century Maritime Silk Road* mention the 2030 Agenda in its priorities section: “We will actively implement the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda and Paris Agreement on climate change. We will advance affordable, reliable and sustainable modern energy services for all, promote clean energy investment and development in relevant countries, and work together to achieve greater energy efficiency” (NDRC *et al.* 2017). These priorities align with SDGs 7 and 13; however, these goals are not mentioned. Such a reference could have strengthened the discourse on the 2030 agenda-BRI synergy.

Similarly, *The Belt and Road Initiative Progress, Contributions and Prospects* recognises the BRI as a means to achieve the 2030 Agenda, specifically referring to the Green Envoy Program. In the context of SDGs 7 and 13, this policy document emphasises the importance of energy and climate cooperation between the BRI states (Office of the Leading Group for Promoting the Belt and Road Initiative 2019).

Belt and Road Cooperation: For A Better World Report includes a chapter on the synergy between the 2030 Agenda and BRI. It links the BRI and specific SDGs. The environmental SDGs, including goals 7 and 13, are a small part of this mapping exercise. The implementation of these two SDGs aligns with the results of the BRI as follows (Belt and Road Forum Advisory Council 2019):

- Improved infrastructure and connectivity; enhanced accessibility of market and resources and productivity; catalysed industry, value and supply chains; accelerated economic growth; and people’s well-being aligned with SDG 7 and 13.
- Improved people’s health and well-being, improved education quality, stimulated innovation, accelerated sustainable economic and social development and enhanced mutual understanding of different cultures and civilisations aligned with SDG 13

The review of Beijing's multilateral environmental diplomacy discourse confirms its commitment to induce BRI-2030 Agenda synergy. Key elements of the project’s environmental governance architecture, including most BRI-specific policy documents, emphasise the BRI’s role in achieving the SDGs. However, this discourse casts doubt on the practical aspects of synergy. First, this discourse lacks detail because only one policy document alludes to a specific SDG. While the

2030 Agenda is a broad concept encompassing the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability, such a reference helps to understand how this synergy can work on the ground, and to what extent it applies to environmental SDGs in particular. Second, China's multilateral environmental diplomacy discourse lacks consistency in its approach to BRI-2030 Agenda synergy. While some policy documents emphasise this synergy, others omit it despite referring to the project's environmental aspects, including energy and climate issues. This inconsistency makes the 2030 Agenda seem like a mere label used in the environmental diplomacy discourse. Third, while this discourse highlights the importance of multilateral cooperation in achieving the SDGs, the constitutive elements of the BRI's environmental governance architecture, such as cooperation platforms and main policy documents, were designed by Chinese governance entities, which seem to supervise the process of greening the BRI unilaterally.

Bilateral environmental diplomacy

The BRI operates mainly via bilateral engagements and memorandums of understanding (MoUs) between China and the BRI host states. MoUs comprise a declaration of intent to cooperate and indicate that a country has become a part of the BRI, but simultaneously fail to reveal whether it has joined any common multilateral institutions or participated in decision-making arrangements that include the BRI's environmental governance architecture. While the media, ministries and embassies indicate that MoUs have been signed, the full texts of most of these agreements are unavailable. However, some joint statements, press releases and communiques between Beijing and BRI countries are available on Chinese government websites. They can serve as a follow-up to bilateral cooperation under the BRI and, most often, as the only available source of the host state's engagement with Beijing. This section analyses 23 bilateral documents between China and BRI states that mention this connectivity project and have been published by the MFA since 2017 (MFA Communiques 2024). The selection of available documents provides information about what engagements Beijing wants international audiences to be aware of. For instance, while BRI energy projects' main recipients include Pakistan, Russia and Saudi Arabia, the Chinese MFA provides only BRI-related statements related to Beijing's bilateral cooperation with Islamabad out of the three states. Most of the accessible bilateral policy documents contain references to environmental and sustainability issues. However, the green elements of the BRI do not seem to be a determining factor for all states involved in the project. Thus, decarbonising and improving environmental standards are not sufficient reasons for joining the BRI.

The available statements between China and the BRI countries related to this project (i) refer to the 2030 Agenda; (ii) mention sustainable development without referring to the 2030 Agenda; (iii) do not mention sustainable development but touch upon energy and climate cooperation, and

therefore have the potential to affect the implementation of SDG 7 and 13; and (iv) entirely omit sustainability and environmental issues.

Following Beijing's multilateral environmental diplomacy under the BRI, the selected bilateral documents mentioned the 2030 Agenda. Specifically, joint communiques and/or statements between China and Vanuatu (MFA 2019a), Papua New Guinea (MFA 2022a), Pakistan (MFA 2022b), Indonesia (MFA 2022c) and the Philippines (MFA 2023a) emphasise these states' commitment to international cooperation vis-à-vis the implementation of the SDGs. In the context of SDGs 7 and 13, China's joint statements with the Philippines assume that they will cooperate in clean energy matters. As stated in bilateral documents, recognising the characteristics of Papua New Guinea and Vanuatu as developing small island countries and their related environmental challenges, Beijing offers assistance in building these states' capacity to address climate change. Interestingly, joint statements between China and the Philippines, Indonesia, Pakistan and Papua New Guinea link the 2030 Agenda with the Global Development Initiative (GDI), which is China's initiative to expedite the implementation of the 2030 Agenda announced by Xi Jinping in 2021. This coupling resembles the common practice in China's multilateral environmental diplomacy under the BRI of linking Chinese eco-concepts – most often the concept of ecological civilisation – with the 2030 Agenda.

Joint statements, communiques and/or press releases between China and Tonga (MFA 2018a), Bangladesh (MFA 2019b), Indonesia (2022d), the Solomon Islands (MFA 2023b) and Nepal (MFA 2023c) assume China's assistance to help these countries achieve sustainable development, without directly referencing the 2030 Agenda. Most of these statements point to energy as one of the areas of cooperation, suggesting the BRI's implications for implementing SDG 7. Specifically, China's bilateral documents with Tonga and Indonesia mention water, solar and wind power. In the context of SDG 13, Beijing has assumed a role in improving Bangladesh's capacity to address climate change. And in the case of the Solomon Islands, Beijing has offered assistance to strengthening this island state's multilateral cooperation mechanisms concerning climate response and disaster prevention and mitigation.

Joint bilateral documents with Maldives (MFA 2017a), Philippines (MFA 2017b; 2018b), Pakistan (MFA 2018c; MFA 2022e), Nepal (MFA 2019c), Brunei Darussalam (MFA 2020a) Tanzania (MFA 2022f) and South Africa (MFA 2023d) do not refer to the 2030 Agenda nor "sustainable development" directly; however, they assume that bilateral cooperation with Beijing can affect the implementation of SDG 7 and/or 13 to varying degrees. The 2018 joint statement between China and Pakistan recognises the early harvest energy projects, mostly coal-based facilities, built and run under the CPEC as satisfactory for both sides, potentially contributing to socio-economic development in Pakistan – however, it does not reference the renewable energy context. Paradoxically, the 2022 China-Pakistan statement emphasises Beijing's support for Islamabad in

developing renewable energy projects, specifically mentioning solar projects and the promotion of green cooperation under the CPEC to align with Pakistan's efforts to combat climate change. This statement also promises to attract Chinese companies to engage in renewable energy projects. Such projects can foster the implementation of SDGs 7 and 13 by improving Pakistan's energy mix to reduce GHG emissions. China's joint statements with Nepal and the Maldives mention cooperation to mitigate climate change. Moreover, the first one refers to the MoU on Energy Cooperation, signed with China, which assumes cooperation and exchange in the fields of renewable energy, including hydropower, wind power, solar power and biomass energy. By potentially enhancing access to energy services and the share of renewable energy, such cooperation aligns with SDGs 7 and 13. Similarly, China's MoU on Cooperation on Oil and Gas Development with the Philippines refers to their energy relationship, which assumes bilateral efforts in maritime oil and gas exploration and the sustainable use of minerals. China's joint statements with Brunei and Tanzania point only to energy as an area of bilateral cooperation under the BRI.

Since 2017, four bilateral documents published by China's MFA have referred to the BRI without paying attention to the environment. Particularly, the *Joint Statement on Deepening Comprehensive Strategic Cooperation between the Islamic Republic of Pakistan and the People's Republic of China* (MFA 2020b) and the *Pakistan-China Joint Press Release* (MFA 2019d) focused on the COVID-19 pandemic and the visits of Prime Minister Imran Khan to China, respectively. However, other accessible CPEC-specific policy documents refer to environmental and sustainability issues to different degrees; thus, generally, these issues are not neglected in this bilateral cooperation, at least according to the official discourse. Other examples of bilateral policy documents that omit the BRI's environmental and sustainability aspects, as climate- and energy-related themes, include the *Joint Announcement Between the People's Republic of China and The Republic of Singapore on the Establishment of an All-Round High-Quality Future-Oriented Partnership* (MFA 2023e) and the *Joint Statement between the People's Republic of China and Nepal* (2018d), which emphasises the strength of bilateral engagements.

The review of China's bilateral environmental diplomacy discourse demonstrates its consistency with the multilateral environmental diplomacy discourse on the BRI-2030 Agenda synergy. Just as policy documents and guidelines have been designed for all BRI states, some statements between Beijing and individual states directly mention the 2030 Agenda. This brings China's multilateral environmental diplomacy discourse closer to its own practice in the BRI states. Another one similarity between these two discourses is that the bilateral environmental diplomacy discourse does not refer to specific SDGs. However, energy- and climate-related themes that align with SDGs 7 and 13 remain the main environmental topics. The main practical barriers to the BRI-2030 Agenda synergy in the related bilateral environmental diplomacy discourse are linked to the

minimal transparency surrounding China’s inroads in most BRI states. In large part, because of the absence of documents, assessing the BRI’s role in implementing SDGs is problematic.

Evidence on the ground

In both its bilateral and multilateral documents China refers to the 2030 Agenda and suggests that in its Green BRI activities it is furthering the relevant SDGs. However, how does this look on the ground? The following table sheds light on this.

BRI Country	SDG 7		SDG 13	
	2017	2023	2017	2023
Pakistan	-	!	+/-	+
Russian Federation	-	!	-	!
Indonesia	-	!	+	+/-
United Arab Emirates	-	-	!	!
Nigeria	!	!	+	+/-
Vietnam	+/-	-	-	+/-
Iraq	-	!	+/-	+/-
Kazakhstan	-	!	-	!
Bangladesh	!	!	+/-	+
Saudi Arabia	-	-	+/-	!

Table 2. Top receivers of BRI’s energy infrastructure and the implementation of SDGs 7 and 13
SDG achieved (+); challenges remain (+/-); significant challenges remain (-); and major challenges remain (!)

Sources: Nedopil. 2021; Sachs *et al.* 2017; Sachs *et al.* 2023.

None of the ten largest BRI energy infrastructure receivers (Pakistan, Russian Federation, Indonesia, United Arab Emirates, Nigeria, Vietnam, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Bangladesh, Saudi Arabia) have improved on their achievements towards SDG 7 since 2017 (Table 2). In contrast, six of them, including Pakistan, the Russian Federation and Indonesia, exhibited a decrement in their achievements. However, the impact of the BRI on such achievements depends on numerous domestic factors such as the proportion of BRI investment vis-à-vis other energy projects, as well as local policies and approaches.

In contrast to the implementation of SDG 7, some of the main receivers of BRI energy investments, including Pakistan, Vietnam and Bangladesh, have improved their performance toward the realisation of SDG 13. In turn, Russia, Kazakhstan and Bangladesh's performance has declined. While Pakistan achieved SDG 13 in 2020, it is important to remember that this goal mostly "measures climate policies, not the effect of these policies" (Nabeel, 2020). While China declares an intention to offer assistance to some BRI states to improve their climate policies, the official documents available between particularly Pakistan and China do not provide details of such cooperation.

Data on the implementation of SDGs 7 and 13 in the top receivers of BRI energy projects challenge China's environmental diplomacy discourse about the synergy between the BRI and the 2030 Agenda. These data resonate more with concerns about the BRI's environmental impact than China's discourse.

Conclusion

This study analysed China's discourse surrounding the Green BRI. Specifically, it assessed the potential of China's environmental diplomacy discourse, assuming that a synergy between the 2030 Agenda and the BRI will be implemented in practice. China's ambition, expressed through its environmental diplomacy discourse suggests that BRI will help participants achieve their SDGs. Evidence suggesting that this part of China's discourse can become a reality includes, first, the significant degree of consistency between multilateral and environmental diplomacy discourses in the way they approach the BRI's role in achieving the SDGs. Both directly refer to the 2030 Agenda and point to similar BRI-related environmental and climate issues. Second, the decrease in China's engagements in coal energy projects vis-à-vis renewable energy projects under the BRI, as revealed by recent BRI reports, can link the BRI with the improvements in SDGs 7 and 13 in the future.

Nevertheless, the extent to which the BRI serves as a consistent and sustainable tool or framework that facilitates the achievement of the 2030 Agenda requires further analysis, particularly from country-based case studies. One important barrier is the lack of access to documentary evidence and an overall opaqueness that stymies research. Moreover, since most BRI states (especially those most heavily invested) are low- and middle-income Global South states (many of which have autocratic regimes or are fragile democracies), information concerning the details of their BRI cooperation with China is opaque and difficult to acquire. A potential lack of civil society insight into the environmental effects of the BRI, the extent of coherence with relevant SDGs and the degree to which a greening of the BRI has occurred are, therefore, difficult to ascertain.

Other barriers are linked to the multilateral environmental diplomacy practiced under the BRI. First, although the BRI's environmental architecture was designed for all participants, it was voluntary for states to join. Second, although China's BRI-related environmental diplomacy emphasises the

importance of multilateral cooperation in mitigating environmental and climate problems, it seems to be unilaterally designed and steered by China.

Furthermore, the foreign policy dimension of the 2030 Agenda raises some questions, which open up future potential avenues of research. Why should China help BRI participants achieve their SDGs, as that is their responsibility? How can we identify how change and progress have been brought about by participation in BRI projects? These questions require intensive case studies to ascertain the existence, degree and nature of linkages. Furthermore, separating the role and effects of China from those of other domestic and foreign factors is problematic.

These practical barriers are confirmed by data on the implementation of SDG 7 in the largest receivers of BRI energy infrastructure. Although the multilateral and bilateral environmental diplomacy discourse highlights China's commitment to deploy investments in renewable and clean energy that contribute to improvements in SDG 7, the states that received the most BRI energy investments noticed a decline or no progress between 2017 and 2023 in achieving this goal. This observation seems to undermine China's multilateral and bilateral environmental discourse on the synergy between the 2030 Agenda and the BRI. Is there a positive correlation between the BRI and SDG-related achievements? To address this question, not only do other endogenous and exogenous factors need to be considered, such as energy investments from other states and existing domestic environment-related factors, but this research also requires more transparency and access to bilateral policy documents between China and BRI host states.

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